

https://web.archive.org/web/20080821202757/http://mems.caltech.edu/courses/E40%20Web%20Files/Supplements/02_Hall_Effect_Derivation.pdf

$$R_H = \frac{1}{e} \frac{p\mu_p^2 - n\mu_n^2}{(p\mu_p + n\mu_n)^2}$$

With $b = \frac{\mu_n}{\mu_p}$

$$R_H = \frac{1}{e} \frac{p - nb^2}{(p + nb)^2}$$

Being $b = 7.9$ or $1/7.9$.

Data from PhysRevApplied 2020, $R_H = 0.208 \text{ cm}^3/\text{C}$

a) Not intentionally doped $\rightarrow p=n$

$$R_H = \frac{1}{e} \frac{1 - b^2}{p(1 + b)^2}$$

$$p = \frac{1}{R_H e} \frac{1 - b^2}{(1 + b)^2}$$

$b = 7.9$ returns $p = -2.3e19$, unphysical

$b = 1/7.9$ returns $p = 2.3e19$, physical, hole mobility is higher

b) Not intentionally doped but doped from defects, whatever they are (like <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/full/10.1021/acsaem.1c01576>) $\rightarrow p = 3e19, n \ll p$

$$R_H = \frac{1}{e} \frac{p - nb^2}{(p + nb)^2}$$

$$eR_H(p + nb)^2 - p + nb^2 = 0$$

$$eR_H b^2 n^2 + (2eR_H b p + b^2)n + eR_H p^2 - p = 0$$

$$n = \frac{-\beta \pm \sqrt{\Delta}}{2a}$$

With $\Delta = \beta^2 - 4ac > 0$ and $\beta = 2eR_H b p + b^2, a = eR_H b^2, c = eR_H p^2 - p$

$b = 7.9$ returns $\beta = 78.18$, $a = 2.08e-18$, $c = -4.8e16$, hence $\Delta = 6.1e3$ and $n = 6.1e14$

$b = 1/7.9$ returns $\beta = 0.269$, $a = 5.33e-22$, $c = -4.8e16$, hence $\Delta = 0.0723$ and $n = 1.8e17$

Both makes sense.

c) Approximation $p-n = 3e19 = \delta$; BTW this is perfectly compatible with the case b) as $3e19 - 2e17 \sim 3e19$ inside the exp. uncertainty.

$$R_H = \frac{1}{e} \frac{p - nb^2}{(p + nb)^2} = \frac{1}{e} \frac{n + \delta - nb^2}{(n + \delta + nb)^2} = \frac{1}{e} \frac{n(1 - b^2) + \delta}{(n(1 + b) + \delta)^2}$$

$$eR_H(1 + b^2)n^2 + (2eR_H(1 + b)\delta - 1 + b^2)n + eR_H\delta^2 - \delta = 0$$

$$n = \frac{-\beta \pm \sqrt{\Delta}}{2a}$$

With $\Delta = \beta^2 - 4ac > 0$ and $\beta = 2eR_H(1 + b)\delta - 1 + b^2$, $a = eR_H(1 + b^2)$, $c = eR_H\delta^2 - \delta$

$b = 7.9$ returns $\beta = 79.18$, $a = 2.11e-18$, $c = -4.8e16$, hence $\Delta = 6.3e3$

thus $n = 6.06e14$ and $p = 3.00006e19$

$b = 1/7.9$ returns $\beta = 1.27$, $a = 3.38e-20$, $c = -4.8e16$, hence $\Delta = 1.61$,

thus $n = 3.8e16$ and $p = 3.0038e19$.

Both make sense again.

If there are NO dopants, hole mobility is higher, if, whatever the reason, unintentional dopants are present, both possibilities make physical sense.

